
**KNOWLEDGE HUB IN PRINCELY STATE OF KOLHAPUR
KARVEER NAGAR WACHAN MANDIR**

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Abstract:

Karveer NagarWachanMandir was the cultural hub in the princely state of Kolhapur. It was the main tool to provide thoughts to the thinkers. The different activities employed by the library and its working producer revealed the change in the society. The punctuality in the working procedure and the timely decisions are ideal even today. The decisions were taken by long deliberations in the general meetings of the library .The first library act was passed by this princely state and implemented for the first time in this country . The politicians were well aware about the important of the library.

Introduction:

Democracy has given people some rights participation in power duties and freedom people got the fundamental right to get Knowledge. We are given local self-governments as Garampanchayat, school, hospital, and library at every village through consternation. The library has become an information centre and guidance cerate. Library helps to make civilized citizen; Libraries become centers to quench the thirsts of knowledge of people. So they become important in human life Kolhapur was the leading princely state having radical thoughts. This state had abandoned orthodox cal thoughts. Karveer Nagar wachan Mandir inculcated progressive thoughts in Kolhapur princely state. We come across the chancing school of thoughts. While taking the historical review of this library. The timely projects employed by this library and the response it got, shows the important role of this library in Kolhapur state.

Kaveer Nagar Wachanmandir: A Historical Review:

‘The Kolhapur native library’ was established in the era of Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj (The Third) Alias Baba Maharaj cloned H.L Anderson established it on 15th June 1850. He called a meeting at Raviwarwada and explained the objective at and benefits of the library. The fund of Rs. 5000/- was collected. The Karveer government contributed Rs. 1000/-out of it. The building of the library was erected by utilizing at Rs. 2508/- There were 17 subscribers at the beginning and monthly income was Rs.15/- There were 442 books at the beginning. Some of those books were given by the Karveer government, Dakshina committees and some missionaries. There were newspapers like Dnyanodaya, Dnyanprakash, Vartaman Dipika and Dhoomketu The head clerk of political department was the administrator of the library. The collected amount was kept in a ‘treasury’ of Karveer government. The construction of library building was started in 1879 and

completed in 1881. Still then that has become the library building. After some Latrines were built from the suggestion of subscribers.

Shri. Vasudeo Rege the secretary published the entire history of the library in august 1917. A condolence meeting was held in 1922 at the death of Rajarshi Shahu Maharaj Chhatrapati Rajaram Maharaj assured to continue the liberal policies of Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj. The library was run under the guidance of government officials till its establishment. The Karveer government helped this library after converting it in to central library.

The silver jubilee of the library was celebrated during 15-11-1931 to 27-11-1931 Chhatrapati Rajaram Maharaj inaugurated the function. Jubilee committee president Shri. Shankarrao Indulakar delivered a speech. He expected that the library should be able to help education and develop interest among people by imparting knowledge.

A special act was made in the state for library in 1944. A meeting was held under the leadership of Prof .N.C. Phadake for converting the library into central library according to the letter of education minister of the state dated 15-7-1944. After long deliberations it was decided to form a committee to discuss with the government. The constitution of the library made by the subscribers and government nominated members was accepted in the annual meeting on 25-2-1945. Shri P. T. Patil, the librarian held the charge as librarian after completing the library Diploma course.

There was a provision in the library act of 1944, that there should be central library and Taluka libraries, Village libraries and mobile libraries. All these libraries would be connected to central libraries. Nearly 15 village libraries were registered and they were given Rs. 100/- fund as primary aid at the sometime some

books were demanded by making 30 boxes for the mobile libraries.

The princely state of Kolhapur was merged in Bombay province on 31st march 1949. The correspondence between the library and curator of libraries of Mumbai Government was started .It was decided that the managements committee should try to maintain the status of this library. While converting it into district library. The Karveer Nagar wachan mandir became the District Library in 1950.

Important Activates:

1) The speeches of Gopalkrishna Gokhale:

Gopalkrishna Gokhale delivered a speech on 'India under British Rule' in the year 1886-87 He also delivered a speech on 'our various Activities' in 1893 and on 'our Educated men' in 1894-95

2) The Elocution competition:

The Elocution competition was the new activity employed by the library in 1932. The Elocution Sabha of Pune assured to give Rs.150/-for this activity. Local 50 participants participated in this activity. Participated from Sangli, Karad were also participated Especially 6 female candidates were also participated.

3) Maharashtra Sahitya Sammelan:

It was decided that the 17th session of Maharashtra Sahitya Sammelan to be held on behalf of the library. The meeting of the Karveer citizen was held .The executive committee and other subcommittees were formed Sayajirao Gaikwad. The Maharaja of Badoda was elected as the president of Sahitya Sammelan. The Sahitya Sammelan began on 17-12-1932. There was a provision of 10,000 people.Chhatrapati Rajaram maharaj arrived at 3 pm and the Sammelan began. In the absence of President Sayajirao Gaikwad, Sardar Madhavrao Kibe elected as the president of Sammelan. The Nayab Divan of Badoda Mane –Patil read out the speech of the president. The

book exhibition was inaugurated by Panjabrao Deshmukh on 28th in the library building. The reception president was Madhavrao Bagal .The Kavi Sammelan was held under the president ship of poet Bhaskarrao Tambe.

4) Golden Jubilee Ceremony:

The Golden jubilee ceremony of the library was held on 29-11-1936 Appasaheb Bhopatkar delivered his speech master Nivaruttinath sung at night.

5) The Honor of poet Madhav Julian:

The famous poet and the member of library Madhav Julian was honored by the then justice of Kolhapur Rao Panditrao, for getting D.Lit. of Mumbai University on 20-12-1938.

6) The Honor of V.S. Khandekar:

The Planned President of Sahitya Sammelan of Solapur V.S. Khandekar was honored under the president ship of poet Girish on 28-3-1941 the president of Dakshin Sahitya Sammelan and the royal poet of Sangli Shri. Sadhudas was honored by the library under the president ship of Shri. V. S. Khandekar.

7) 94th Anniversary of the Library:

The 94th Anniversary of the library was celebrated under the president ship of Bhai S.A. Dange at Rajaram College.Bhai Dange delivered his speech on 'Effects of world war on Marathi'Literature .Shri. Gajananrao Watave sung lyrics at night.

8) Centenary of the Library:

It was decided to celebrate the centenary of the library in general meeting in 1950 It was also decided to celebrate the centenary under the president ship of chief minister Balasaheb Kher between 15th may to 21st may ,1950.But the programmed was postponed due to the illness of Balasaheb Kher.

9) 300th death anniversary of saint Tukaram:

The 300th death anniversary of saint Tukaram was celebrated according to the suggestion of Maharashtra sahitya parshad-in1950.The speeches were

delivered by Dr.R.C.Shrikhande Prof. P.N.Kulkarni .Bhajans and sermons were also performed.

Such type of various activities was undertaken by the library and they were beneficial to the people of Kolhapur state.

Special Events:

Many special events are happened up to 1950 in the history of the library. It revels about the procedure of the library .These events hilled to sow the seeds of progressive thoughts in the Kolhapur state some of these events are as follows.

- One association named vaktruttottejak Joined the library in 1873 This association held the program me every year for two days in kagalkar wada and distributed prizes This association gave gold medal to Bala Govind Lohar in 1875 for making excellent knives. The association also declared prizes of Rs.100/- for excellent production of paper, sugar and pencils.
- One special incident took place in 1879-80 A sweepers Dhanu Vallad Emam applied for membership to the library. The library was running with the help of social help and sympathy so his application was denied .The working committee took that decision in its meeting on 5-10-1879
- Sou. Lasmiabai Ruikar was appointed in the Managing committee of the year 1898-99 but she was not present for a single meeting so the members lost 1/12 of rights. It was mentioned in the report that if the members from present and liable were appointed, would have been good decision.
- The new rules of the library were passed in 1884. They were passed in the 8 meetings of general.
- Shri.Bhaskarrao Jadhav work a letter on 01-10-1902, to arrange a lecture of Prof. Rajaram Shastri at the

library .The managing committee did not approve it. The organizers did not agree with progressive opinions of Prof. Shastri. The orthodox cal policies of the organizers helped to stars a movement in the future.

- The resolution was passed in 1909 to collect important articles published in the newspapers. The responsibility of marling English articles was given to Shri.Visgwanathrao Gokhale and Prof. Latthe and for Marathi articles it was given to Shri. Y.Abhyankar.
- A catalogue of English books was published in 1910 under the guidance of Bhaskarrao Jadhav. The subscribers read about 13500 books because of that catalogue.
- Shri.Balkrushn karkhanis a drawing master of Technical school made oil painting of Chh.Shahu Maharaj so Rs.300/-sanctioned to buy and hang it in the hall of library. It was bought for Rs.250/- That painting was reveled on 2-4-1911
- The secretary of the library Shri.Balaji Modak suggested that other libraries should establish at taluka places in the state in the state in 1871. This suggestion was implemented in the course of time.
- Shri. Bhaskarrao Jadhav was appointed as president and Madhav Dongare was appointed vice president in 1911. The elected 12 members of managing committee were from all castes and creeds.
- Rs. 141/- were stolen away in 1913 because of the neglect of the librarian Apatate. So it was decided that the bonus amount of Apatate would be compensated by the library.
- Major Graham gifted his own book entitled ‘The statistical Report on the principality of Kolhapur’ to the

library. Shri.Bapusaheb Govindrao jadhav borrowed the book in 1911-12 but did not return it. So a registered notice was sent to Jadhav in 1917. He did not accept it. So it was decide to file a petition against Shri.Jadhav so the book was returned to the library in 1919.

All those events in the life of the library helped to develop the reading culture in the state those incidents revealed the change that has taken place in the state. Karvee nagarWachan Mandir had become the cultural hub in the era of princely state of Kolhapur. The library helped to inculcate the radical thoughts of Chh.Shahu Maharaj among the subjects. So it has grand value in the history of the state.

Conclusion

Karveer Nagar wachan mandir was the cultural hub at the time of princely state of Kolhapur. It was the centre to provide thoughts to scholars. It also inculcated progressive thoughts among society through different activities. The annual meeting of the library was held timely. The new directions were shown through deliberations. The work of the library is ideal even today.

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